

Angle-Action Coordinates for Bars

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Outline

- Why AA-coords?
- An introduction to torus mapping
- Elements of Hamiltonian perturbation theory; resonances
- Examples: corotation, OLR, ILR
- Summary
- AA-coords and solar wind kinematics
- Conclusions

AA coordinates

- Galaxies are comprised of orbits
- Most orbits are regular (have 3 conserved quantities)
 - Even chaotic orbits are likely superpositions of regular orbits
- Actions J are the only orbit labels that can be complemented by canonically conjugate (angle) coordinates θ
- Regular orbits are 3-tori labelled by $J_i = \frac{1}{2\pi} \oint d\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{v}$
- Regular orbits are quasi-periodic (have 3 fundamental frequencies Ω)
 - Frequencies are v important dynamically
- If you know $(x, v)_{(\theta, J)}$ you can compute anything you could possibly want to know about any orbit
 - Much richer information than time sequence $(x, v)_t$

Traditional view

- Given a Hamiltonian $H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})$ find the generating function S of the canonical transformation

$$(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) \xleftrightarrow{S(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{J})} (\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{J}) \text{ such that } H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) = H(\mathbf{J})$$

- Since $\mathbf{v} = dS/d\mathbf{x}$, S satisfies the Hamilton-Jacobi (H-J) eqn

$$H\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial \mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{x}\right) = E$$

- We solve by separation of variables introducing 2 new constants I_2, I_3 . Then we compute $J_j(E, I_2, I_3)$
- Problem: H-J eqn for rotating bar can't be solved by sep of variables
- Even in axisymm case H-J eqn can be solved only for special (Staeckel) Φ

Torus mapping

- We start from toy AA-variables (θ^T, \mathbf{J}^T)

$$(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{J}) \xrightarrow{S(\mathbf{J}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^T)} (\boldsymbol{\theta}^T, \mathbf{J}^T) \xrightarrow{\text{toy}} (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) \xrightarrow{\text{point trans}} (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{V})$$

- Where $X(\mathbf{x})$ is a point transformation and

$$S(\mathbf{J}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^T) = \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\theta}^T + \sum_{\mathbf{n}} S_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{J}) e^{i\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\theta}^T}$$

- For given \mathbf{J} choose $S_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{J})$ to minimise variance of $H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})$ over grid in θ^T

- The outputs are:

$$\{S_{\mathbf{n}}\}, \quad H_0(\mathbf{J}) \equiv \langle H(\boldsymbol{\theta}^T, \mathbf{J}) \rangle_{\boldsymbol{\theta}^T}, \quad \{h_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{J}, \boldsymbol{\theta})\}, \quad \left\{ \frac{\partial S_{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \mathbf{J}} \right\}, \quad \Omega_0(\mathbf{J})$$

- Compute tori on a grid in \mathbf{J} and then extend H_0 , Ω_0 , etc to arbitrary \mathbf{J} by interpolation

- Then have AA-cords for 'unperturbed' H_0 and a perturbing Hamiltonian $\{h_{\mathbf{n}}\}$ so we can do Hamiltonian p-theory

Application to bars

- We need to be in the bar's rotating frame:

$$H_{\text{rot}} = H_{\text{in}} - \Omega_b p_\phi$$

- We decompose $H_{\text{in}} = H_{\text{axisymm}} + H_{\text{bar}}$
- By torus mapping we decompose $H_{\text{axisymm}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) = H_0(\mathbf{J}) + \{h_{\mathbf{n}}\}$
- Then we've an 'unperturbed' Hamiltonian and a perturbation

$$H_{\text{rot}} = (H_0 - \Omega_b J_\phi) + (\{h_{\mathbf{n}}\} + H_{\text{bar}})$$

Hamiltonian p-theory

- Hamilton's equations for dJ/dt and $d\theta/dt$ have terms $e^{in.\theta}$
- In 1st-order p-theory we set $\theta = \Omega_0 t$ and integrate
 - Divergent results as $n.\Omega_0 \rightarrow 0$ (small divisors; resonances)
- We identify N that gives smallest frequency $N.\Omega_0$ and change to new AA variables (θ', J') that have $\theta'_1 = N.\theta = \theta_s$ -- the slow angle
$$J_s = J'_1 = J_1/N_1, \quad J'_2 = J_2 - N_2 J_s, \quad J'_3 = J_3 - N_3 J_s$$
- We average Hamilton's equations over the fast angles θ'_2 and θ'_3
- In this approx. J'_2 and J'_3 are constant and we are left with a Hamiltonian H_s for motion in the (θ_s, J_s) plane
- Contours of H_s are our orbits

How important are resonances?

Closed x_1 x_2 orbits

Circulating inside ILR

Trapped by ILR

Corotation (B2018)

- In rotating frame Ω_ϕ goes from >0 inside CR to <0 outside, so near CR Ω_ϕ is the slow angle and $\mathbf{N}=(1,0,0)$
- J_r and J_z conserved but non-trivial motion in (θ_ϕ, J_ϕ) plane
- Orbit switches between 2 values of J_ϕ

OLR

- $N=(2,0,1)$
- $J_\phi - 2J_r$ & J_z const

ILR $N=(2,0,-1)$

- Perturbations v strong
 - Raises technical issue – negative actions
- Resolve it with new cords in (θ_s, J_s) plane (B2020)
- In weak bar orbits circulate at $\langle J_{\phi_{res}} \rangle$
- Blue plots $H_s(X, p_x)$ on a ladder's rung

Perfectly resonant
tori

ILR of strong bar

- On rungs up ladder: sharp transition trapped/free
- On lower rungs: the transition is continuous

The story so far

- Resonances play a central role in galaxy dynamics
- Resonance only meaningful in context of an unperturbed $H(J)$
- We can construct AA-coords, $H(J)$ and δH with torus mapping
- H p-theory reduces problem to motion in slow plane governed by H_s
- In simple cases trapped/untrapped dynamics given by pendulum eq
- But with torus mapping it's possible to markedly upgrade traditional pendulum eq
- At ILR & OLR dynamics at low J_r can't be approximated by pendulum eq: trapped/untrapped is no longer a clean division
- Dynamics largely unaffected by value of J_z

Resonances and the solar nhd

- Orbits that come close to the Sun are strongly biased

UV space at Sun – ~7000 visiting tori

Very non-uniform J-space grid needed to get ~uniform V-space grid

Star streams

- Dehnen 1999
- Gaia DR3
- Asymmetry in U implies non-uniformity in θ_r

Associated with features in J space

Trick+2019

And in θ -space

- Likely associated with resonances

Hunt+ 2019

In small boxes strong selection effect

- Stars on left/right edge have apo/peri near Sun
 - Over-represented because loitering

Features wash out with wider selection

- Overall $f(J)$ smooth because perturbed in θ as well as J
- Hamiltonian p-theory describes this

All DR3 RVS

Conclusions

- Torus mapping opens the dynamics of barred galaxies to Hamiltonian p-theory
- P-theory is central to physics: it defines even the concepts we use to understand phenomena
- The accuracy with which p-theory reproduces orbits is astonishing
- Orbits are perturbed in both θ and J in a coordinated way
- Local V -space strongly biased in both θ and J
- We are still far from full exploitation of the data